

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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MUNDARIJA

ПРИНЦИПЫ ПЕРЕХОДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ, СУЩЕСТВУЮЩИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВНЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ	12
Набиев Дилмурод Хамидуллаевич	
YaSHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLASH TIRISH TA'SIRIDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TRANSFORMASIYASI	19
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xo'jaevich	
РОЛЬ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ТРУДА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЕГО ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ	26
Гулямов Саидахор Саидахмедович, Икрамов Мурат Акромович, Очилов Акрам Одилович	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASH MAQSADIDA "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT"GA O'TISH ZARURATI	33
O.X. Hamidov, D.Sh. Yavmutov	
ESG-ИНСТРУМЕНТАРИЙ КАК ФАКТОР УСИЛЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	38
Татьяна Юрьевна Анопченко, Сергей Вадимович Ревунов, Роман Вадимович Ревунов	
TRANSITION OF RUSSIAN REGIONS TO A CLOSED-LOOP ECONOMY	49
Nikonov Sergey Mikhailovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Filipenko Alexander Alexandrovich	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNING MOHIYATI VA TUZILISHI	53
Navruz-Zoda Baxtiyor Negmatovich	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК ДРАЙВЕР УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА И МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ РАБОЧИХ МЕСТ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	59
Зокирова Нодира Каландаровна	
KREATIV IQTISODIYOT VA UNING INDUSTRIYA TURLARINING NAZARIY MASALALARI	64
Mamayunus Pardaev, Obid Pardaev, Akram Ochilov	
EKOLOGIK OMILLARNI HISOBGA OLGAN HOLDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHDA ERISHISH	73
Saidov Muhammadali Hakimovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Esanbekov Diyorbek Mirzabek o'g'li	
INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOTCHILIK MAHSULOTLARI KOOPERASIYASINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	81
Raxmatulla Ergashev	
KARTOSHKA MOSLANUVCHAN NAVLARI TURLI EKISH MUDDATLARI VA MULCHALASHLARDA HOSILDORLIGI HAMDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI	86
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Toshpulatova Surayyo Tulqin qizi, Ismayilov Alisher Isroilovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHNING KALITI	90
Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanakovich, Usmonov Murodjon Dusmurot o'g'li	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ» В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	93
Сайёра Насимовна Хамраева	
SABZAVOT (SHIRIN) MAKKAJO'XORI AJRATILGAN MOSLANUVCHAN NAV-DURAGAYLARINI ASOSIY VA TAKRORIY EKINLAR SIFATIDA TURLI MUDDATLARDA YETISHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	97
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Nurillaev Ilhom Xolbek o'g'li, Jabborov Botir Shukurovich	
ZAMONAVIY BOZOR MUNOSABATLARIDA SAVDONI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY VA USLUBIY JIHATLARI	101
Ivatov Irisbek	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	105
Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich, Abdiyeva Flora Botir qizi	
GREEN ECONOMY: GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE AND UZBEKISTAN'S PATH	110
Dilmurod Mirza-Akhmedovich Rasulev, Dildorakhon Ulugbek kizi Shomuradova	

ОЛИЙ ТА'ЛИМ ХИЗМАТЛАРИНИ RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TARG'IB QILISH BO'YICHA XORIJ TAJRIBASI	113
Musayev Bekjon Shukurillayevich	
TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINI BARQAROR STRATEGIK RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN USULLAR TAHLILI	116
Turdibekov Xasan Ibragimovich	
ЗЕЛЁНОЕ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЕ И ФАКТОРЫ ЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	120
Орипов Ильхом Абдуллаевич	
Перспективы развития цифровой трансформации в Республике Узбекистан	128
Мусабеков Джорабек Хакимджанович, Воронин Сергей Александрович	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNING MUHIM OMILI SIFATIDA.....	133
G.Erkayeva	
Barqaror ish o'rinlarini yaratishda yashil iqtisodiyotning o'рни	138
Qo'chqorov G'aybulla Fayzullayevich, Qo'ziyeva Shaxnoza Bozor qizi	
ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	141
Фазлитдин Бахадирович Аминов	
RESPUBLIKADA EKOLOGIK TOZA MAHSULOT YETISHTIRISH ASOSIDA ELEKTRON SAVDONI RIVOJLANTIRISH	145
Q. J. Mirzayev, F. F. Ulug'murodov	
Qoraqalpog'istonda sanoatni restruktizatsiyalash va yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish: muammolar, istiqbollar va statistik tahlillar	150
Abipova Gulmira Salavatdinovna	
CHORVACHILIK XO'JALIKLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AGLOMERATSIYANING AHAMIYATI.....	153
Xusainov Oybek Jabborovich	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA STRATEGIYASINING KOMPANIYA UCHUN AHAMIYATI.....	156
Ergashev Toxir Kurbanovich, Toxirova Nigora Zokirjon qizi	
CHORVACHILIK KLASSTERLARI VA AGLOMERATSION RIVOJLANISH: O'ZARO TA'SIR VA SYNERGIYALAR	161
Xusainov Oybek Jabborovich	
HUDUDLARNING INNOVATSIYON SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASH	165
J.A. Ismatullayev, A. Do'lanov	
СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	171
Нафасов Тохиржон, Г. П. Эркаева	
Mamlakatimizda ishsizlikni kamaytirishga qaratilgan islohotlar.....	174
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich	
USE OF THE ADVANCED EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES OF FARMING AND HOUSEHOLDS	178
Ochilova Nargiza Akramovna	
SHAHAR AGLOMERATSIYALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI.....	181
Xidoyatova Nigora Shorakibovna	
IQTISODIY O'SISHDA MEHNAT MIGRATSIYASINING AHAMIYATI.....	184
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Saidakbarov Jamshid Ne'matullo o'g'li	
TURIZMNIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TRANSPORT XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	189
Qosimov Jahongir	
РЫНОК ГОСТИНИЧНЫХ УСЛУГ В ТУРИЗМЕ В УСЛОВИЯХ ДИВЕРСИФИКАЦИИ И ДЕМОКРАТИЗАЦИИ ГОСТИНИЧНОЙ ИНДУСТРИИ	192
Ташмаматов Садирдин Нажмиддинович	

O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASIDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KADRLAR MALAKASINI OSHIRISHDA DUAL TA'LIMDAN FOYDALANISHNI BOSHQARISH	196
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Xamidova Mo'tabarxon Abdumalik qizi	
MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA AUTSORSING XIZMATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	201
Nasiba Ergasheva	
KORXONALARDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISHNING ASOSIY TAMOYILLARI	207
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Nurullayeva Vazira O'ktamovna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИИ: ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ И РИСКИ	211
Номазов Бахром Бобомуратович	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ПРИНЦИПОВ ESG В ФИНАНСОВУЮ СФЕРУ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	215
Алимова Азиза Шерзатовна	
THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON MANAGEMENT	219
Ergashev Tokhir Kurbanovich, Tohirova Nigora Zokirjon kizi	
O'ZBEKISTONNING "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT STRATEGIYASI" NI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING ZARURIYATI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	224
Ergasheva Nazira Muratovna, Soyibov Mirjon Bekjonovich	
ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ УСЛУГ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИХ НА ПОВЫШЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ И КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ	227
Алимова Муниса Юлчиевна	
РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОБУВНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЕЁ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЗНАЧИМОСТИ.....	232
Расулов Нозимжон Набиджонович	
AGLOMERATSIYA VA IQTISODIY O'SISH: SABAB-OQIBAT ALOQASI (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	236
Xidoyatova Nigora Shorakibovna	
KORXONALARNING SOLIQ IDORALARIDA HISOBGA OLINISHIDAN HOSIL BO'LGAN ORTIQCHA TO'LOVLARINI BOJXONA TO'LOVLARIDA HISOBGA OLISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	239
Boykabilov Bahodir Mustafaevich	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLARGA INVESTITSIYALAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	242
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
ORGANIK QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA "IXTISOSLASHTIRILGAN AGROKOOPERATIV" TASHKIL ETISH ORQALI TA'MINOT ZANJIRI BOSHQARUVINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	248
Amirqulov Shuxrat Olimovich	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING MOLIVAVIY RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHI UCHUN ZAMONAVIY HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	254
Xayriddinov Shuxrat Botirovich	
TURIZMNING MADANIY-TARIXIY RESURSLARI: ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALAR VA TAMOYILLAR	258
Ruzmanov Dilshod Usmanovich	
BARQAROR TURIZM DESTINATSIYALARINING SIG'IMINI VAHOLASH METODIKASI.....	262
Ibroximov Nodirbek Xasanovich	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫЕ ИСТОЧНИКИ ЭНЕРГИИ КАК ОСНОВА ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	266
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ МАРКЕТИНГ И ПОВЕДЕНИЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЕЙ.....	272
Раимова Муборак Джураевна	
"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" NING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI	276
Djumayev Asqar Xaydarovich	

RAQAMLI MARKETINGNING ISTE'MOLCHI XULQ-ATVORIGA TA'SIRI.....	281
Raimova Muborak Jurayevna, Dilmurodov O'tkir	
HUDUDNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI	287
SH.A. Buriyev	
SAVDO XIZMATLARINING ASOSIY FAOLIYAT KO'RSATKICHLARI TIZIMINI BAHOLASH.....	291
Muxamedova Aziza Ravshanovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA GLOBAL IQLIM O'ZGARISHI: YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING IQLIM O'ZGARISHINI YENGISHDAGI O'RNI VA GLOBAL HAMKORLIK.....	295
Usmonov Murodjon Xolmurod o'g'li, Ulug'bek Eshmaxmatov	
КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ МЕХАНИЗМА НАЛОГОВОГО АДМИНИСТРИРОВАНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	299
Абдулов Дамир Рустамович	
О'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH ISTIQBOLLARI	305
Yuldashev Shamsiddin Qiyamiddinovich, Boliyeva Baxora Farxodovna	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА: КОНЦЕПЦИИ, ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ.....	308
Туляганова Шахноза Самукджановна	
О'ТА ERTAGI TARVUZNING HIMOYALANGAN JOYLAR UCHUN MOSLANUVCHAN NAV VA DURAGAYLARINI AJRATISH, ULARNI TURLI O'G'IT ME'YORLARIDA HOSILDORLIGI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	311
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Amirov Xamidulla Suyunovich, Umirova Durdona Muqum qizi	
ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ПЛОДООВОЩНОЙ ОТРАСЛИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	315
Уралов Элшод, Вельм М.В.	
DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY AS A MODEL OF PROGRESS IN HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	320
Abdiev Alimardon	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СЕКТОРА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЫ И РАЗВИТИЯ КАДРОВОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА.....	322
Мухаммадбобур Салимов	
КИЧИК BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR.....	326
Suyunov Jabbor Mahmudovich	
“SALOHİYAT” TUSHUNCHASINING MAZMUNI VA IQTISODIY-IJTIMOIIY MOHIYATI.....	331
Zoirov G'olibjon Toshtemir o'g'li	
DAVLAT BOSHQARUVIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKTDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI	334
Salimov Muhammadbobur Qodir o'g'li	
O'QUV JARAYONLARINI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	337
Tilakov Sherzod	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING XALQARO TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING AHAMIYATI.....	340
Sattarov Umirzoq, Ro'ziev Zafar Ikromovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT XOM ASHYOLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	343
Xazratov Sarvar Ibragimovich	
YURTIMIZDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASHNING ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	348
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, O'rinov Diyorbek Xolmo'min o'g'li	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI O'QUV MARKAZLARI VA KURSLARINI BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	353
Tilakov Sherzod Akbarovich	

SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MAHSULOT ISHLAB CHIQRARISH VA SOTISH SIFATI HAMDA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	357
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Ziyodullayeva Marjona Alisher qizi	
OMMAVIY TADBIRLAR YORDAMIDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: O'ZBEKISTON VA XALQARO TAJRIBA.....	360
Ibragimov Sardorbek Xusanovich	
Анализ цифровой трансформации и её влияния на привлечение инвестиций в регионы Узбекистана.....	365
Рахмонова Дурдона Хасан кизи	
Korxonada moliyaviy salohiyatini baholashning statistik tahlili.....	370
M.O. Musurmonova	
DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF THE BANKING SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Kadirov Lutfulla Khalimovich	
PROBLEMS OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE LABOR MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR THEIR SOLUTION.....	381
Sharopov Temirmalik Rustam o'g'li	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ORQALI QASHQADARYO VILOYATI SANOAT KOMPLEKSINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	385
U.Shukurov	
FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN SERVICE INDUSTRIES	390
Hazratkulov Shahboz Boboqul ogli	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA TA'LIMNING ROLI.....	394
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISHI UCHUN DAVLAT TOMONIDAN YARATILAYOTGAN IMKONIYATLAR.....	398
Xudoyorov Azizbek Avaz o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA TA'LIM SIFATINI YAXSHILASHNING XORIY TAJRIBASI.....	404
Safarov Sh. S.	
IJTIMOYIY MENEJMENTDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	408
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, Davronova Farangiz	
«ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ ФИНАНСОВЫЙ КОНТРОЛЬ: КАЗНАЧЕЙСКИЙ КОНТРОЛЬ В БЮДЖЕТНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ».....	415
Файзуллаева Зилола Равшановна, Д.Х. Пулатов	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING ASOSIY JIHLATLARI.....	421
Urozoza Shaxlo Hasan qizi, Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI	427
Safarov Shoxrux Sattor o'g'li	
PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN.....	431
Alimardonova Gulfizoda Alimardon kizi	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA KAPITAL QO'YILMALAR HISOBINI TO'G'RI TASHKIL ETISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	434
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA KICHIK BIZNESNING IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	441
Berdimurodova Farzona Bahodir qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING BIZNES VA IQTISODIYOTDAGI ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	446
Davronova Farangiz Ilhom qizi	

ZAMONAVIY RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA PUL VA BANK TIZIMLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ISTIQBOLLARI HAMDA AHAMIYATI	452
Axtamova Ozoda Ulug'bek qizi, Cho'liyeva Gulsanam Yulchi qizi, G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTI: TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNING ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI	460
N. Qo'ziboyeva	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTINI TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLAR ORQALI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ZARURATI.....	466
Vayskulov Ramazon Alisher o'g'li	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA TURIZM KLASTERLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA IQTISODIY INTEGRATSIYA.....	470
Xushvaqto'v Ramziddin	
ILMIY SALOHİYAT VA OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINING UZVIY BOG'LIQLIGI: TAHLIL VA TAVSIYALAR	476
Muratov A'zam Alisher o'g'li, Ochilov Akram Odilovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: GREEN CREDIT.....	480
Eshtemirova Ma'rifat Akram qizi, Kabilova Shaxnoza Jurayevna	
DEHQON XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI NARXLARINING DINAMIKASI VA BOZOR MUVOZANATI MODELLARINI QO'RISH.	483
Ergashov Yashnarbek Istamovich	
The Role of Renewable Energy in the Green Economy.....	488
Khudoyberdiyeva Olima, Yakhshikulova Mokhinur	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish: asosiy muammolar va imkoniyatlar	494
Jumanazarov Asilbek Utkirbek o'g'li, Ulug'bek Eshmaxmatov	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING RAQOBAT USTUNLIGI ORQALI BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH OMILLARI	498
Ro'ziqulov Jamshid Ulug'bek o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH SIYOSATINING ZAMONAVIY TRENDLARI HAMDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI.....	504
Shodiyev Jahongir 504	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: O'ZBEKISTONNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	509
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna, Sh. S. Sa'dullayev	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI SOHASIDA MAHSULOTLAR INTENSIV RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH JARAYONLARI	512
Saburov Jumanazar Salievich	
SUG'URTA XIZMATLARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI VA MEXANIZMLARI.....	516
E.Sobirov	
“YASHIL IQTISODIYOT”GA O'TISH ORQALI TABIIY RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING ATROF-MUHITGA SALBIY TA'SIRINI KAMAYTIRISH	520
Xo'janova Gulshoda Otamurodovna	
QISHLOQ JOYLARDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KONSEPTUAL YO'NALISHLARI	526
Dilafroz Taylakova	
KORXONALARDA EKOLOGIK INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI TAHLILI.....	532
Ulashov Aliboy Rashid o'g'li	
YURTIMIZDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA BANK VA MOLIYAVIY TIZIMLAR UCHUN YANGI IMKONIYATLAR TAHLILI HAMDA KELGUSIDAGI ISTIQBOLLARI	538
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, Alarov Asilbek Oybek o'g'li	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIGI VA EKOLOGIK IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH MASALALARI.....	545
O'rinov Diyor, Xolliyev Sh.B.	

YASHIL IQTISODOYOT VA UNDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR.....	549
Ermuminov Elbek Erkin o'gli, Ilmiy rahbar: Yaxshiqulova Moxinur Toxir qizi	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA KADRLARNING TUTGAN O'RNI	553
Turayeva Nargiza Rustamovna	
IQTISODIYOTDA TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	557
G.P.Erkayeva, N.H.Qo'ziboyeva	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING AHAMIYATI VA O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH STRATEGIYASI	560
Samadova Jasmina Sherali qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
"YASHIL" ENERGETIKA VA "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT.....	564
Qarshiyeva Dilsora Ismoil qizi, Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
MAMLAKAT BUDJETINING SHAKLLANISHI VA DAROMADLAR TAQSIMOTINING IQTISODIYOTDAGI ROLI	569
Ashirqulova Sevinch Sarvar qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	574
Urozoova Shahlo Hasan qizi, Rahmonova Tillaoy Malik qizi	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHINING KO'RSATGICHLARI.....	579
Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanakovich, Usmonov Murodjon Dusmurot o'g'li	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI TARTIBGA SOLISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	583
Mirzayev Qulmamat Djonuzoqovich, Mirzayev Azzamjon Jonuzokovich, Eshquvvatova Nodira Abdullayevna	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA IQTISODIY RESURLARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	588
Mirzayev Qulmamat Djonuzoqovich, Eshquvvatova Nodira Abdullayevna	
СТРАТЕГИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИЙ И ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОГО КАПИТАЛА В ЭПОХУ НООНОМИКИ.....	593
Чекулаева Кристина	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПРИ ПЕРЕХОДЕ К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	599
Чекулаева Кристина	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – MAMLAKAT TARAQQIYOTINING ASOSIY OMILI.....	605
Oybek Hamdamov, Qosimov Jahongir	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA INSON KAPITALI SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA TA'LIMNING AHAMIYATI	608
M.Ostanova, Ro'ziyev Ramshid	
MODERN LEGAL BASIS FOR THE EFFICIENT USE OF FINANCIAL RESOURCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN OUR COUNTRY	613
Ismoilova Gulrux, Khayriddinov Shukhrat Botirovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SHAROITIDA TABIIY - IQTISODIY MANBAALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMI	617
Mavlonov Shaxzod Shahobiddin o'g'li, Mavlonova Surayyo Xasan qizi	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA SOHALARNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI	621
Gulrux Arslon qizi Ismoilova	

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN SERVICE INDUSTRIES

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Abstract: This article explores the risks that arise in attracting investments in service sectors and their foreign experience in managing them, including ways to regulate investment activities in the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, France, China, Japan.

Key words: investment, investment activities, stock market, production, legislation, credit organizations, investment activity, investment, risk management, financial diversification, insurance system, digital technologies.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlariga investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda yuzaga keladigan risklar va ularni boshqarish bo'yicha xorijiy tajribasi o'rganiladi, jumladan, AQSH, Buyuk Britaniya, Germaniya, Fransiya, Xitoy, Yaponiyada investitsiya faoliyatini tartibga solish yo'llari o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: investitsiya, investitsiya faoliyati, fond bozori, ishlab chiqarish, qonunchilik, kredit tashkilotlari, investitsion faollik, investitsiya, risklarni boshqarish, moliyaviy diversifikatsiya, sug'urta tizimi, raqamli texnologiyalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется зарубежный опыт управления рисками при привлечении инвестиций в сервисные сети, в том числе способы регулирования инвестиционной деятельности в США, Великобритании, Германии, Франции, Китае, Японии.

Ключевые слова: инвестиции, инвестиционная деятельность, фондовый рынок, производство, законодательство, кредитные организации, Инвестиционная активность, инвестиции управление рисками, финансовая диверсификация, система страхования, цифровые технологии.

Currently, the sustainable growth of investment volumes and their effective use is one of the tactical and strategic tasks. Its successful solution involves a comprehensive consideration of the complex interdependence of many elements of the investment sphere inherent in the investment process. It is known from the experience of economically developed countries that the consistent implementation of the relationship between micro and macroeconomic reproduction is possible only with the market as a self-regulating system and with the regulatory investment activity of the state. The service sector is one of the most important structural elements of the modern economy. The development of this sector directly affects the level of economic growth and employment. Therefore, attracting investments to the service sector is one of the important strategic issues. However, various risks may arise in the process of attracting investments. This article analyzes the risks that arise when attracting investment in the service sector and foreign experience in managing them. Fundamentally improving the investment climate, reducing the state's participation in the economy, ensuring the inviolability of private property, and increasing its role and significance are important conditions for the sustainable development of the country's economy. In the current global economic climate, countries that have established

and implemented excellent investment policies are leading the world. For example, these countries include the G7 countries. The experience of Japan, the USA, Great Britain, Germany and France, in particular, is one of the most optimal solutions for investment activities. Their economic development strategies are countries whose economic development strategies can be the best experience for our country.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

A number of scientific research works have been conducted by foreign economists in this area. In particular, Y.S. Melkumov analyzed the effective use of financial, property and intellectual investments in financing investments in order to obtain profits in the development of production and entrepreneurship [1]. The author here studied investments as a source of income and indicated the types of investment activities. The controversial issue here is the types of investment objects. This has been discussed in our other scientific works.

S.V. Valdaytsev and P.P. Vorobyev analyzed the sources of financing for social investment. They concluded that the funds spent on social income generation processes are intended to generate higher income or social benefits in the future [2].

According to Prof. Y.M. Mirkin, a realistic, promising form of investment financing is to increase the placement of companies' savings from the secondary market into equity capital, but the level of this source of investment financing is very low [3].

The well-known economist W. Sharp also pays special attention to the mechanism of financing investment activities through the stock market. In his opinion, a rational investment strategy with a direct relationship between the profitability and riskiness of securities is the basis for financing investment activities. Financial intermediaries (commercial banks, savings and credit associations, credit unions, insurance companies, mutual funds, pension funds) indirectly provide corporations with the opportunity to attract additional funds from the stock market [4].

K.K. Khasanov has conducted a comparative analysis of the legal regimes, institutional norms and mechanisms of investment activity in developed foreign countries. Criteria for assessing investment activity and ways to increase the activity of regions in attracting foreign investment using the experience of foreign countries are proposed [5].

Associate Professor B.K. Tukhliyev's research considered a number of issues, including financing investment activities, the formation of their sources, the creation of a favorable investment environment, the study of factors affecting investment activities, and the improvement of the activities of enterprises with foreign investment. Conclusions and proposals were formulated on the composition, analysis, and improvement of investment activities and sources of financing them in the current conditions [6].

It should be noted that effective regulation of this sector is one of the most important ways to develop the country's economy. Therefore, it is important to conduct necessary research in this area and find ways to regulate investments and create mechanisms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The article uses analytical and comparative methods. The experience of foreign countries in attracting investments in the service sector is studied, their risk management strategies are analyzed. Statistics from open sources, scientific articles, and reports of international organizations are also used.

Rating categories for each region of the country based on the ratio of total capacity and integral risk magnitudes

Group	Rating category
1A - group	High authority – minimal risk
1B - group	High-potential – moderate risk
1C - group	High authority – high risk
2A - group	Medium-strength – minimal risk
2B - group	Medium-capable – moderate risk
2C - group	Medium authority – high risk
3A1 - group	Has a low level of authority - has minimal risk
3A2 - group	Has insignificant authority - has minimal risk
3B1 - group	Low-level authority – moderate risk

3C1 - group	Low-level authority – high-level risk
3B2 - group	Has insignificant authority - has a moderate level of risk
3C2 - group	Has insignificant authority - has a high level of risk
3D - group	Low-level authority – extreme risk

During our research, we analyzed the processes of regulating investment activities in developed countries. According to our analysis, in the United States, investment processes are regulated by the state within certain limits. More than 22% of gross capital investments in the US economy are accounted for by states, of which 14% are allocated to investments from the federal budget. The state's influence on investment activities is carried out using such financial instruments as preferential income tax rates, accelerated depreciation policies, and incentives for selected categories of investments.

Due to the federal structure of the state, foreign investment in the United States is regulated in two ways: at the federal level and at the state level. At the federal level, general regulatory requirements are mainly established, and special regulatory requirements for the participation of foreign investors in projects in the territory of the respective states are established by local authorities. Each state operates in attracting foreign investment on the basis of local laws and long-term and short-term programs developed taking into account local characteristics and needs. Each state has its own programs for attracting domestic and foreign investment, since the federal government does not play an active role in determining the goals of economic development of a particular region of the country. Local authorities independently determine promising areas for the development of industrial sectors, both at the expense of state and borrowed funds.

The policy pursued in the United States, with some exceptions, is to ensure equal conditions for the management of foreign and domestic investors. For example, foreign investors can freely invest their funds in most sectors of the country's economy, as well as withdraw capital and profits.

In Europe, in particular in Germany and Sweden, investment projects are being implemented on the basis of social responsibility and corporate cooperation in order to minimize risk in the service sector. For example, companies make investments taking into account environmental and social accountability. This, in turn, reduces risk, as this model helps to maintain corporate reputation and develop strategies aimed at social progress.

Although there is no specific law regulating foreign investment in France, there is a system of "prior notification of the authorities of the intention to extend the approval period". This mainly applies to investors from non-EU countries engaged in the activities of a French company. In addition, French law clearly distinguishes between direct and other foreign investments, which is explained by the use of more favorable regulation in relation to the latter. This is because, despite the significant simplification of the procedure for regulating foreign investment, the majority of direct investment transactions in France still require prior notification of intention or prior authorization.

In Japan, intelligent platforms and "real-time" analysis have become popular in the service sector to minimize risk. With the help of such analytical tools, companies are able to identify development trends in advance and thus clearly see any risks. For example, many Japanese companies have implemented systems that allow them to quickly respond to changes in the market by installing real-time monitoring.

The main methods of regulating investment activities in the UK, France, Germany and Japan are as follows:

The main methods of regulating investment activities in the UK, France, Germany and Japan are as follows:

- regulation of the total volume of capital investments. This is the main method of managing the investment process, which is carried out through credit interest rate policy, monetary policy, tax and depreciation policy;
- selective promotion of investments in specific enterprises, sectors and areas of activity through credit and tax incentives, for example, investment loans;
- direct administrative intervention in the investment process in order to launch or withdraw certain production capacities by coordinating the plans of large corporations.

In France, relations between the state and the regions are built on a contractual basis within the framework of the national planning system. The state thus assists in the economic development of the regions. Each region concludes planned contracts with the state, which bind both parties to a specific investment program. Then they are included in the state's national plan as a priority task. At the same time, additional funds are being allocated to the most problematic regions. The implementation of such a policy is carried out in the form of restructuring the regional economy. For this purpose, investment grants are allocated to improve the infrastructure of the regions and create jobs in priority sectors of the economy.

To equalize the imbalance in the development of regions, the experience of state financing of France and Germany began to be actively used at the European Union level, for which a special Structural Fund of the

European Union was created. This fund collects funds from all EU member states. And only those countries with the most problematic regions in terms of economic development receive funds. The resources of such funds are replenished not only at the expense of budget revenues, but also on the basis of attracting free funds of the Austrian National Bank.

Japan and China are actively using state budget funds and various forms of savings of citizens to finance the most important structural projects of the economy, which are built mainly on a network basis.

In China, lending to the economy is entrusted to the banking system. The main types of lending are commercial and political lending. In commercial lending, interest rates on loans, as well as lending directions, are formed on the basis of market principles. "Political lending" is intended to play the role of the main instrument for implementing state economic policy. For this purpose, three state development banks have been established in China. At the same time, the state budget is the main source of funds for "political lending".

In Japan, the budget deficit at all levels, as well as state-owned enterprises, is financed mainly by citizens' savings, since the Trust Fund Bureau is the main subscriber of government bonds in the primary market and the main buyer in the secondary market. The Bureau manages the state pension system, citizens' savings in postal savings banks, and insurance deposits. The Bureau's funds and government bonds are used to finance large infrastructure development projects that do not have direct commercial interests in the private sector. Such financing is carried out through the Investment and Loan Program, which is adopted annually by the country's parliament.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

From the above, it can be seen that state regulation of the investment process is a system of legislative, executive and supervisory measures implemented by authorized state bodies to stimulate investment activity and, on this basis, economic growth.

The state's activity in regulating the investment process is influenced by the state and level of development of the market economy, its level of orientation towards solving social goals and tasks. However, in all cases, this regulation is a complex process that includes goals, subjects, objects and means.

Foreign experiences in analyzing and minimizing risks when attracting investment in service sectors provide effective directions through innovative and intellectual methods, social responsibility, cooperation and monitoring. The practical application of such methods and experiences in Uzbekistan also creates great opportunities for strengthening the production and service sectors and minimizing risks.

Therefore, based on the world practice of organizing investment attraction into the economy, it would be appropriate to create a clear and stable legislative framework for the state, as well as to form an appropriate system of regulation of investment activities, primarily by the state, in the person of specially authorized bodies.

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